

Enhancing coping skills for management trainees in SMEs: A training programme based on coping effectiveness intervention

Zhuofeng Li
University of Edinburgh (United Kingdom)

lipiandex@gmail.com

Copyright. 2024. Psychreg Journal of Psychology
Published by Psychreg Ltd
ISSN: 2515-138X

Prior research suggests that management trainees often experience various sources of stress, particularly within SME environments brimming with changes, pressure, and uncertainties. However, rare studies have explored psychological interventions for them to enhance their work performance. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to equip management trainees with systematic stress coping techniques to enhance their self-efficacy in stressful work situations. The study referred Lazarus and Folkman (1984)'s *Transactional Theory of Stress and Coping* as the theoretical lens, and employed Anshel (1990)'s COPE approach as the intervention routine to design the coping training programme. The programme, namely *Coping Effectiveness Training* (CET) intervention ($n = 20$), includes intervention timelines, systematic coping repertoire, coping exercises, and follow-up evaluations by eight progressive sessions. The intervention is illustrated based on empirical evidence from literature in neuropsychology and psychophysiology. Significantly, this study contributes to providing both academics and practitioners with a scientific coping training framework to enhance management trainees' self-efficacy, facilitate them adapting to the new work environment, and improve job performance.

Keywords: coping effectiveness intervention; management trainee; self-efficacy; stress coping; SME

Management trainees are future leaders of companies. However, in the small and medium-sized enterprises (hereafter referred to as SMEs) environment, they might face bigger stress due to steeper learning curve (Yawised et al., 2021), early-on responsibility (Mughal, 2023), and less support (Beltramino et al., 2020). Compared to large-scale companies, SMEs are often in the status of insufficiency of resources. Consequently, trainees must face a steeper learning curve that might be more overwhelming (Yawised et al., 2021). Second, SMEs tend to be more agile, suggesting them face a quicker pace of work changes. Therefore, they might be given early-on responsibilities and will feel increased stress to perform (Mughal, 2023). Third, SMEs are often less structured or supportive on readily available support systems such as established training programmes (Beltramino et al., 2020). In addition to the SME work environment, this group of population also experiences a series of external stressors such as passive relocation from job transitions, workplace ostracism, or knowledge hiding from colleagues (Melrose, 2019; Riaz et al., 2019). All these kinds of stressors will possibly lower their self-efficacy and hamper their work performance. Therefore, to mitigate these stressors and enhance their self-efficacy, it is pivotal to provide management trainees with appropriate interventions to help them cope.

Implementing stress coping training can assist performers in dealing with stressful situations, leading to their performance enhancement (Joshi et al., 2021). The *Coping Effectiveness Training* (CET) intervention, a cognitive-behavioural theory-based intervention, emphasises the matching of performers' coping strategies and stressors (Reeves et al., 2011). It is underpinned by the cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) aiming at changing individuals' cognition and reinforcing effective coping skills subsequently (Van der Klink et al., 2001). It is deemed appropriate to generalise in the competitive or volatile environments such as sports, military and business (Nahlén Bose et al., 2016). However, studies focusing on psychological interventions for management trainees are rare (Eby et al., 2019; Fusar-Poli et al., 2021). On the other hand, self-efficacy is an important mediator in the relationship between individuals' coping effectiveness and job performance (Ebner et al., 2018). Therefore, it is imperative to develop a scientific coping training programme, which can help this group navigate the aforementioned stressors, adapt to the working environment, and enhance self-efficacy.

In this paper, the CET intervention will be individual-based, incorporating coping strategies, coping exercises, coping appraisal, and so on. Additionally, the programme will also focus on developing effective communication skills, leadership skills, and problem-solving skills to assist management trainees navigating the challenges of their roles. It is important to note that a comprehensive coping training programme should be an ongoing process, rather than a one-time event (Eby et al., 2019). To ensure the long-term success of the programme, it should be regularly evaluated and updated based on feedback from both mentors and themselves (Nahlén Bose et al., 2016). As such, this will facilitate SMEs providing a more supportive environment that promotes employee well-being, foster personal growth, and ultimately, drive business success.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Transactional Theory of Stress and Coping

The theory, developed by Lazarus and Folkman, has been particularly fundamental in shaping stress and coping research over the past five decades (Cooper & Quick, 2017). The theory emphasises the cognitive phenomenological processes that enable individuals to appraise their environment, emphasising the relational and dynamic nature of the transaction where stress may arise (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). This appraisal process generates emotions, and when stimuli are appraised as 'threatening, challenging, or harmful' (i.e., stressors), the resultant distress initiates coping strategies to manage emotions or attempt to address the stressor itself. Coping processes produce an outcome (i.e., a change to the person-environment relationship), which is reappraised as favourable,

unfavourable, or unresolved. As noted, the primary features of the theory are (a) cognitive appraisal, and (b) coping.

Cognitive appraisal

Lazarus and Folkman (1984) described two core forms of appraisal: primary appraisal and secondary appraisal. Primary appraisal ascribes meaning to a specific individual–environmental transaction, and determines the significance of this transaction to an individual’s well-being, manifesting as positive, irrelevant, or stressful. Furthermore, secondary appraisal determines what can be done to manage the stressor and its resultant distress (Dewe & Cooper, 2007). Within this theory, coping strategies aim to either directly manage the stressor (i.e., problem-focused coping), or regulate emotions arising as a consequence (i.e., emotion focused coping). Overall, the theory emphasises that the coping process is a continuous cycle of transactions between the individual and environment to resolve this disequilibrium.

Coping effectiveness and Goodness-of-fit hypothesis

Coping effectiveness can be usefully conceptualised as strategies that reduce negative outcomes and increase positive outcomes. The effectiveness of such a given coping strategy is dependent on how well the coping strategy corresponds with appraisals and situational conditions. Therefore, the critical components determining coping effectiveness are fit and context. Lazarus and Folkman (1984) emphasised that effective coping depends on the fit between the context and coping. A central contextual characteristic is controllability, the degree to which individuals can change the conditions of a stressful situation. As such, their coping goodness-of-fit hypothesis argues that problem-focused coping is effective in situations with high controllability (Person & Frazier, 2024); conversely, if individuals cannot alter the stress-evoking contexts, emotion-focused coping is considered more effective for less controllable circumstances (Wolfers et al., 2024). According to this hypothesis, we taxonomise sources of stress into controllable and uncontrollable stressors to integrate them into the model of the theory. See Figure 1.

Figure 1

Transactional Model of Stress-Coping

Source: adapted by the author based on Lazarus and Folkman (1984)

Coping taxonomies and their mechanisms with self-efficacy

Attentional control

Attentional control refers to one's ability to selectively focus on certain things (while ignoring others) which are closely related to executive functioning, including conflict resolution, reasoning, psychological resilience, task switching, work memory, planning, as well as initiation and monitoring of actions (Shi et al., 2019). Also, it is useful to control performers' emotions especially at the beginning of work and predict better performances. Attentional control and self-efficacy may share some neural underpinnings and they overlap in brain circuits, including the anterior cingulate cortex (ACC), adjacent medial prefrontal cortex (PFC) and lateral PFC. These brain areas play a key role in regulating attention and self-efficacy (Tang et al., 2022). High self-efficacy may enhance the function of PFC, thereby improving the individual's attentional control and executive functioning when faced with challenges. Moreover, high self-efficacy may also reduce the amygdala's response to stress (a key brain area that processes emotional responses), thereby reducing anxiety and fear, which can help improve attentional control (Tang et al., 2022). Empirical research further demonstrated that lower attentional control resulted in lower performance without threat perception, but individual performance could improve under threats with higher attentional control, especially when threats were from uncontrollable stressors (Grillon et al., 2016).

Thought stopping

Thought stopping is a technique in CBT. It is used to help individuals interrupt or change negative or unwanted thought patterns. The technique usually involves an external signal, for example, saying the word 'STOP' or using a gesture, to get the individual's attention and interrupt the current flow of thought. Thought stopping, as a coping strategy, may help reduce stress responses and the release of cortisol, thereby reducing the impact of negative thoughts on emotions and behaviours and promoting positive thoughts, ultimately improving self-efficacy (Bakker, 2009; Cowan et al., 2017). This technique is introduced at the early stage of performers' enrolment in fostering their emotional control ability to cope with prospective stressful situations in work (Laela et al., 2018). Bakker (2009) conducted a meta-analysis of thought stopping, and concluded that it can be highly effective if it is applied judiciously within a CBT model. It can enhance an individual's coping repertoire. Moreover, this effect appears to be stronger than any possible concurrent dilution of habituation effects in exposure therapy (Bakker, 2009).

Relaxation response

Relaxation response refers to a physiological state of parasympathetic dominance—a state in which there is greater activation of the parasympathetic nervous system in relation to the sympathetic nervous system. The parasympathetic and sympathetic nervous systems are two branches of the autonomic nervous system which work alongside one another to initiate, sustain, or dampen a variety of physiological functions throughout the body. The parasympathetic nervous system is colloquially known as the 'rest and digest' system, whereas the sympathetic nervous system is chiefly involved in the stress response, also known as the 'fight or flight response.' (Luberto et al., 2020). The relaxation response is believed to be an integrated hypothalamic response which results in generalised decreased sympathetic nervous system activity (Benson, 1985). Elicit relaxation often includes slowed diaphragmatic breathing, centring, etc. Perceived relaxation response attests to positively correlate to self-efficacy (Kulmatycki & Boroń-Krupińska, 2019; Lim et al., 2014). Additionally, relaxation response technique is effective for new staff to mitigate stress at work particularly when they are motivated by mentors (Calder Calisi, 2017; Formanoy et al., 2016).

Mental simulation

Mental simulation refers to the cognitive process of imagining or visualising an event, action, or scenario in one's mind as if it was happening in real-time. This process is closely linked to mental models and imagery, allowing individuals to predict outcomes, solve problems, and navigate complex

situations by rehearsing potential actions and their consequences in a vivid mental space (Zhong & Zhang, 2021). Neuroscientific studies suggest that mental simulation activates similar brain regions as those used during actual experiences, emphasising its potential for real-life applications (Waytz et al., 2015). Moreover, research indicates that mental simulation can influence motivation and self-efficacy by enabling individuals to visualise successful outcomes (Dogan et al., 2021). For example, Paravlic et al. (2020)'s study showed that it exerted a positive effect on both the single and dual-task conditions during rehabilitation. On the other hand, according to the CBT theory, self-efficacy is presented in two dimensions in the context of sports decision-making: (1) Confidence in successfully predicting and choosing the right response, and (2) efficacy in executing the selected response. This suggests that self-efficacy is closely intertwined with the decision-making and execution process, and mental simulation, thereby, can enhance self-efficacy by improving such capabilities (Kleka et al., 2024).

Positive-thinking

Positive-thinking is implicated to be cultivated to cope with stress and to enhance job performance during performers' utilisation and reappraisal of coping strategies (Thomaes et al., 2020). Research has shown a positive correlation between positive thinking and self-efficacy that it may enhance an individual's sense of self-efficacy because it involves the interplay of cognitive and emotional processes, especially in the pursuit of goals (Alkhatib, 2020). Specifically, positive thinking (e.g., future-oriented thinking) is highly associated with the prefrontal cortex (MPFC) and the posterior cingulate cortex (PCC) in the brain system, both of which are connected with personal goals. Besides, MPFC and PCC are similar to the key areas involved in self-affirmation techniques (e.g., self-talk), suggesting that future-oriented thinking and self-affirmation possibly rely on similar neural mechanisms and reinforce each other (Cascio et al., 2016).

Social support

Social support is recognised as a key mediator of job performance from the research on 211 traffic workers (Baruch-Feldman et al., 2002). The research results showed that the traffic workers' perceived quality of social support at work was correlated with some core performance outcomes such as performance ratings and occupational satisfaction. Social support enhanced self-efficacy, which in turn promoted performers to employ more adaptive coping skills (Denton et al., 2014). It suggests that seeking social support during the intervention is of highly importance to enhance performers' coping ability with different stressors.

Coping exercise

Diary and Albert Ellis' ABC model can be used as coping exercises to help performers identify and challenge negative thought patterns. For example, the ABC model (acronym of "Antecedents" or "Activating event", "Beliefs", "Consequences"), a tool in CBT, can be utilised to track a consistent reflection on performers' stressors, build mental resilience, and help them recognise their irrational thoughts and beliefs (Selva, 2021). The goal of the ABC model is to learn how to use rational thinking to respond to adverse situations in a healthy way. It is effective in treating depression, anxiety, addiction, rehabilitation, and other mental health conditions (Paudel, 2020). Also, diary provides a good means of organising thoughts and completing self-reflection (Grossmann et al., 2021).

Figure 2
The ABC Model

Source: Ellis (1991)

METHODS

Participants

The proposed coping training programme targets 20 management trainees, consisting of fourteen men and six women. The purpose of the programme is to provide support and coping strategies to these participants who are experiencing intense stress from taking on multifunctional responsibilities and adapting to a new organisation. As Formanoy et al. (2016) suggest, this situation can be particularly challenging for novices, making CET intervention a pragmatic tool for their professional development. The samples involved in this programme age from 21–26 years old. They are assigned to different departments and responsible for preliminary managerial tasks. During the programme, they work alongside current departmental managers who act as their mentors, guiding them through their roles and providing necessary support. The participants are responsible for various tasks, such as data-analysis, task delegation and supervision, feedback and communication, as well as resources control.

Procedures

Throughout the CET intervention, the participants will learn various coping techniques that will help them manage their stress levels more effectively. The programme consists of eight sessions that cover topics including time management, cognitive-behavioral techniques, coping exercises, and follow-up measurement. In addition to these sessions, they will have access to one-on-one coaching sessions with experienced mentors who specialise in work-related stress management.

As for the procedure of the intervention design, Anshel (1990)'s COPE approach, reflecting the progressive 'Control emotion, Organise input, Plan responses and Execute actions', incorporates cognitive and behavioural coping techniques that mirror real-life settings, and is presented based on the serial utilisation of such techniques chosen to cope with stressful situations (Wurst, 2016). Therefore, the CET intervention designed is in conformity with the progressive steps of the COPE approach (Anshel, 1990).

Measurement

Measurement is an important follow-up component in how an individual perceives, reacts and behaves within the transaction of stress and coping (Lipshits-Braziler et al., 2017). In this regard, the Coping Self-Efficacy (CSE) Scale questionnaire and Coping-Effectiveness (CE) Scale questionnaire provide a measurement of an individual's perceived ability to cope with life challenges and to evaluate changes in CSE and CE during the CET intervention (Chesney et al., 2006). These

questionnaires consist of 26 items and are based on the works of Chesney et al. (2006) and Gottlieb and Rooney (2004).

Intervention design

The programme consists of a 6-week block CET intervention, a 2-week maintenance session, a mid-term follow-up held during week 4, and an end-term follow-up at the end of week 8. Table 1 provides a detailed overview of the programme structure. Before the intervention and after the maintenance session, the participants are required to complete self-evaluations through the CSE Scale and CE Scale questionnaires.

The CET intervention is designed to help participants cope with the stressors that arise from the steeper learning curve and multifaceted responsibilities. Self-evaluation is also a pivotal component of the programme, as it provides a baseline measurement of the participants' CSE and CE before the CET intervention, and helps track their progress throughout the programme. By completing the questionnaires, they can identify areas where are needed to improve and can gain a better understanding of their coping skills and effectiveness.

Table 1
Framework of CET intervention sessions and coping exercise

Week	Session Theme	Duration	Coping Exercise
Week 1	Understand own stressors and coping ability	60 min	Diary
Week 2	Control emotion	60 min	Diary
Week 3	Organise input	60 min	ABC model
Week 4	Plan response	60 min	Diary
	Mid-term follow-up (without CSE & CE questionnaires)	2 days	
Week 5	Execute	60 min	ABC model
Week 6	Seek social support	60 min	Diary
Week 7–Week 8	Maintenance	2 weeks	ABC model
End of Week 8	End-term follow-up	2 days	
	Self-evaluation with CSE & CE questionnaires	45 min	

Independent variable

The independent variable is the CET intervention based on Chesney et al. (2006)'s CET framework, which provided a theoretical coping foundation to our intervention and has been successfully adapted in Reeves et al. (2011)'s research. The CET framework involves stressful scenario evaluation, problem-focused and emotion-focused coping strategies, social support utilisation, and the correlations between stressors and coping strategies.

Dependent variable

CSE and CE are the dependent variables of the CET intervention (Lamb et al., 2016). CSE is measured through the 26-item CSE scale (Chesney et al., 2006), and CE is measured through the CE scale (Gottlieb & Rooney, 2004). Participants will complete self-evaluations in the format of 5-score Likert scale. For example, 1-score means "definitely cannot do", and 5-score means 'definitely can do' (Chesney et al., 2006).

Baseline

Participants will complete the questionnaires by person in a quiet and comfortable environment one day before the intervention is implemented. A formative perspective can be followed to evaluate whether or not the increase of self-efficacy by the CET intervention will be beneficial to their coping

effectiveness. Therefore, two measurement time periods (i.e., intervention and post-intervention) are set to conduct the coping training programme.

Intervention Implementation

The CET intervention enables participants to reflect on the controllable and uncontrollable stressors, master and apply corresponding coping techniques, and review their practices periodically, then employ new coping techniques progressively (Reeves et al., 2011).

Session 1: Understand own stressors and coping ability

This session aims to introduce the concept of stress and coping, develop their awareness of stressors and coping responses. First, participants reflect on their stress and coping experiences in life. The *Transactional Theory of Stress and Coping* and the COPE approach are introduced. Meanwhile, mentors disseminate exemplars on how they cope with stressors, so that participants can anticipate stressful events to remove anxiety. Participants elaborate their understandings of stressful situations among working scenarios after the session. The home-assignment requests them to identify five individual strengths that facilitate them in coping effectively.

Session 2: Control emotion

In this session, participants' emotion control skill will be equipped. It is to cultivate their emotion-focused coping with uncontrollable stressors (e.g., peer pressure from different individual backgrounds). They are instructed to focus on situations' appraisals and identify which stressors can be changed, and which cannot be. They are taught how their appraisals may affect physiological, emotional and behavioural status. For instance, participants should understand their thinking errors and utilise thought stopping technique (e.g., closing eyes, changing visual field) (Ruddell et al., 2018). Furthermore, they should practice these techniques at work. In the homework assignment, they sort out their emotions and review how to better cope in similar situations.

Session 3: Organise Input

This session enables participants to evaluate the accuracy and feasibility of the perceived information to set attainable and measurable objectives (e.g., efficient data-analysis). First, participants review the actions of Session two. Second, as work goes deepened, more uncontrollable stressors (e.g., workplace ostracism, office politics) may occur. Therefore, it is important to solidify emotion-focused coping strategies, particularly the relaxation skill (Reeves et al., 2011). Specifically, two relaxation techniques are cultivated: *rhythmic breathing* and *centring*. Participants need to match specific stressors with their emotion-focused strategies, then create a realistic coping plan when these stressors occur. Third, participants should employ these skills in their coping plan. In the home-assignment, they use the ABC model to identify positive elements from their coping plan to self-recognise their progressive coping ability.

Session 4: Plan response

This session helps participants to learn to make planning and preparations for potential errors and anticipated stressful situations. Some problem-focused coping strategies (e.g., mental simulation) are introduced to manage controllable stressors (e.g., project demonstration). First, participants reflect on the above emotion-focused sessions, home-assignments and emotion-focused coping skills in specific business scenarios. Second, since mental simulation is a well-timed technique to facilitate improving skills and performance, especially when participants set a primary or contingency plan, it is deemed appropriate to employ in this phase before their execution of work, so that they can rehearse a stressful situation to reduce stress and strengthen the coping ability. With this approach, participants can identify controllable stressors and the strengths and weaknesses of their coping responses, then connect these stressors with the learned coping techniques. Third, participants review particular error work cases, and discuss how they will cope with such errors with

the problem-focused coping skills learned in this session, and then, transfer the learned at work. Fourth, they are assigned to write a positive case of themselves as home-assignment (Seligman et al., 2005). See Figure 3 for the training flow of this session.

Figure 3
 Training flow of plan response

Session 5: Executive

This session aims to extend participants’ problem-focused coping repertoire to cope with controllable stressors (e.g., perfectionism). It advocates the behavioural coping skills, self-talk and positive-thinking. First, participants reflect on Session 4, including the learned coping techniques and their applications at work, and summarise home-assignments. Second, they are asked to sort out different coping strategies and fit them into respective stressors. They should elaborate on why the coping strategy is suitable for the relevant stressor. Based on the learned mental simulation technique, participants start to adopt this coping exercise to realise on-site stress coping. Third, they are encouraged to use positive-thinking and self-talk so that optimistic emotions can be reinforced. Some scenarios are designed to scrutinise their comprehension in the utilisation of self-talk and positive-thinking. They need to employ these learned coping skills at work ultimately. Fourth, in the home-assignment, ABC model is employed to mark their positive thinking, and reappraise their stress coping strategies at work. During all the above sessions of intervention, continuous feedback is vital as it facilitates them realising their strengths and weaknesses in coping with stress. Meanwhile, the practicing time will be gradually reduced alongside enhanced feedback opportunities. The training flow of the executive session can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4
 Training flow of executive session

Session 6: Seek social support

This session aims to strengthen participants' understandings and utilisation of social support. First, they reflect on their problem-focused coping skills, home-assignments and application of coping techniques at work. Second, they are taught that social support categorises into problem-focused and emotion-focused support. Problem-focused support principally comes from organisational support, leader-member exchange, and supervisor consideration. Emotion-focused support mainly comes from friends, family, and peers (Denton et al., 2014). Third, after identifying their own support network and rate how often they engage with each other (Baruch-Feldman et al., 2002), participants classify their social support members into the above two categories. Fourth, participants map the stressors into relevant social support members, and develop an action plan and communicate with them to obtain real support. The home-assignment requires participants to record effective utilisation of social support to manage their stressors.

Session 7: Maintenance session

With reference to Chesney et al. (2006), a maintenance session is reserved for participants after the intervention. It assists them to improve their learned coping skills and transfer them into work. In addition, it offers participants opportunities to review whether any clarification or support is needed.

Session 8: Follow-up (Week 4 and 8)

First, participants are debriefed by mentors, and join monthly 2-day workshops, complete online module evaluations to track their execution of coping strategies. They also join a half-day "live review" organised by mentors and one additional human resources personnel to discuss their progress and feedback from mentors and subordinates. The role of human resources personnel is to ensure the objective and justice of the interview outcome. Second, participants finish the CSE and CE questionnaires after the programme to measure the intervention effectiveness and their changes. Third, manipulation check is conducted to evaluate the practical significance of the intervention. According to Hrycaiko and Martin (1996), this assessment includes three questions: (1) How important is the ability to cope with stressors? (2) Is the intervention process acceptable? (3) Are you satisfied with the progression of the coping-skill mastery?

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSION

Stress and coping in the workplace context for particular populations is consistently a growing research area that researchers attempt to learn more about how such populations negotiate stressful situations. However, there is minimal research on exploring management trainees' stress coping (Eby et al., 2019; Fusar-Poli et al., 2021). Therefore, this study sought to fill in this gap by designing a CET intervention programme from a transactional perspective within their stressful situations. By filling this research gap, this study aims to provide management trainees with systematic coping repertoire to cope. Specifically, the study helps participants to respectively identify the controllable stressors (e.g., project demonstration, data-analysis) and uncontrollable stressors (e.g., workplace ostracism, peer pressure), employ corresponding coping strategies (i.e., problem-focused and emotion-focused coping) throughout the programme to fit in their environment, conduct ongoing coping exercises (i.e., diary, ABC Model) to appraise their personal and environmental situations from transactional perspectives, then employ new coping techniques progressively. Importantly, follow-up assessments (i.e., CSE and CE questionnaires) are also indispensable to measure the participants' CSE and CE. The programme will make a significant contribution to the field of human resources management from individual-based, psychological intervention perspective.

In conclusion, this study designed a coping training programme using CET intervention for management trainees based on systematic literature review with empirical evidence. It is important to iterate that, from the transactional perspective of Lazarus and Folkman (1984)'s *Transactional Theory of Stress and Coping*, this study employed Anshel (1990)'s COPE approach as the intervention-

design procedure to incorporate cognitive and behavioural forms of coping strategies for the group of population to cope with stressful circumstances. The CET intervention, followed eight progressive sessions of coping repertoire (e.g., positive-thinking, mental simulation), mirrors the real business setting. Through the progressive steps of the sessions, the programme design implicates to facilitate mitigating management trainees' stress, enhancing their self-efficacy, and helps them accommodate to the new work environment more readily.

There are unique strengths of this study. This is the first study as we know of to design a CET intervention exclusively for management trainees. Therefore, it is of great practical significance to benefit this group of population in coping with various sources of stress (i.e., controllable and uncontrollable stressors) in work. Second, this study systematically discussed the core coping taxonomies in current research, and synthesised their mechanisms with self-efficacy—a significant predictor influencing individuals' stress CE and work performance. The systematic review on the coping repertoire based on empirical evidence in the fields of neuropsychology and psychophysiology greatly strengthens the scientific nature of our intervention design. This leading-edge CET intervention design, which is applied in the business setting, sets an exemplar for both academics and practitioners.

There are also some limitations of this study. First, the intervention does not take individual differences into consideration, which might lead to possible variations of the programme effect. In this regard, the author would consider involving individual differences to entail the intervention specifics in future research. Second, this study merely illustrates the core coping taxonomies which have been demonstrated effective to lower stress and enhance self-efficacy in prior research. However, they are not exhausted and there are remaining coping techniques which were uncovered in our programme design. Therefore, consistent efforts should be made to explore the mechanisms between the comprehensive coping repertoire and self-efficacy.

Acknowledgements: None declared

Conflict of interests: None declared

Funding: None declared

Ethical approval: University of Edinburgh

REFERENCES

- Alkhatib, M. A. H. (2020). Investigate the Relationship between Psychological Well-Being, Self-Efficacy and Positive Thinking at Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 9(4), 138–152. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1258951>
- Anshel, M. H. (1990). Toward validation of a model for coping with acute stress in sport. *International Journal of Sport Psychology*, 21(1), 58–83. <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/full/10.5555/19901884825>
- Bakker, G. M. (2009). In defence of thought stopping. *Clinical Psychologist*, 13(2), 59–68. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13284200902810452>
- Baruch-Feldman, C., Brondolo, E., Ben-Dayan, D., & Schwartz, J. (2002). Sources of social support and burnout, job satisfaction, and productivity. *Journal of occupational health psychology*, 7(1), 84. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1076-8998.7.1.84>
- Beltramino, N. S., García-Perez-de-Lema, D., & Valdez-Juárez, L. E. (2020). The structural capital, the innovation and the performance of the industrial SMES. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 21(6), 913–945. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIC-01-2019-0020>
- Benson, H. (1985). Stress, health, and the relaxation response. In *Behavioral medicine: Work, stress and health* (pp. 15–32). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-009-5179-2_2
- Calder Calisi, C. (2017). The effects of the relaxation response on nurses' level of anxiety, depression, well-being, work-related stress, and confidence to teach patients. *Journal of Holistic Nursing*, 35(4), 318–327. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0898010117719207>
- Cascio, C. N., O'Donnell, M. B., Tinney, F. J., Lieberman, M. D., Taylor, S. E., Strecher, V. J., & Falk, E. B. (2016). Self-affirmation activates brain systems associated with self-related processing and reward and is reinforced by future orientation. *Social cognitive and Affective Neuroscience*, 11(4), 621–629. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scan/nsv136>
- Chesney, M. A., Neilands, T. B., Chambers, D. B., Taylor, J. M., & Folkman, S. (2006). A validity and reliability study of the coping self-efficacy scale. *British journal of health psychology*, 11(3), 421–437. <https://doi.org/10.1348/135910705x53155>
- Cooper, C., & Quick, J. C. (2017). *The handbook of stress and health: A guide to research and practice*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Cowan, C. S. M., Wong, S. F., & Le, L. (2017). Rethinking the role of thought suppression in psychological models and treatment. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 37(47), 11293–11295. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2511-17.2017>
- Denton, F. N., Rostosky, S. S., & Danner, F. (2014). Stigma-related stressors, coping self-efficacy, and physical health in lesbian, gay, and bisexual individuals. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 61(3), 383. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0036707>
- Dewe, P., & Cooper, C. L. (2007). Coping research and measurement in the context of work related stress. *International Review of Industrial and Organizational Psychology 2007*, 141–192. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470753378.ch4>
- Dogan, B., Pattison, N., & Alinier, G. (2021). A form of mental simulation with significant enhancements enabling teamwork training. *International Journal of Healthcare Simulation*. <https://doi.org/10.54531/JSHC9951>
- Ebner, K., Schulte, E.-M., Soucek, R., & Kauffeld, S. (2018). Coaching as stress-management intervention: The mediating role of self-efficacy in a framework of self-management and coping. *International Journal of Stress Management*, 25(3), 209. <https://doi.org/10.1037/str0000058>
- Eby, L. T., Allen, T. D., Conley, K. M., Williamson, R. L., Henderson, T. G., & Mancini, V. S. (2019). Mindfulness-based training interventions for employees: A qualitative review of the literature. *Human Resource Management Review*, 29(2), 156–178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmmr.2017.03.004>
- Ellis, A. (1991). The revised ABC's of rational-emotive therapy (RET). *Journal of rational-emotive and cognitive-behavior therapy*, 9(3), 139–172. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01061227>
- Formanoy, M. A., Dusseldorp, E., Coffeng, J. K., Van Mechelen, I., Boot, C. R., Hendriksen, I. J., & Tak, E. C. (2016). Physical activity and relaxation in the work setting to reduce the need for

- recovery: what works for whom? *BMC Public Health*, 16, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-016-3457-3>
- Fusar-Poli, P., Correll, C. U., Arango, C., Berk, M., Patel, V., & Ioannidis, J. P. (2021). Preventive psychiatry: a blueprint for improving the mental health of young people. *World Psychiatry*, 20(2), 200–221. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wps.20869>
- Gottlieb, B. H., & Rooney, J. (2004). Coping effectiveness: determinants and relevance to the mental health and affect of family caregivers of persons with dementia. *Aging & Mental Health*, 8(4), 364–373. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02699931.2015.1024614>
- Grillon, C., Robinson, O. J., Mathur, A., & Ernst, M. (2016). Effect of attention control on sustained attention during induced anxiety. *Cognition and Emotion*, 30(4), 700–712. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02699931.2015.1024614>
- Grossmann, I., Dorfman, A., Oakes, H., Santos, H. C., Vohs, K. D., & Scholer, A. A. (2021). Training for wisdom: The distanced-self-reflection diary method. *Psychological Science*, 32(3), 381–394. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797620969170>
- Hrycaiko, D., & Martin, G. L. (1996). Applied research studies with single-subject designs: Why so few? *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology*, 8(2), 183–199. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10413209608406476>
- Joshi, K., Sochaliya, K., Modi, B., Sharma, L., Singh, S., & Kartha, G. P. (2021). A study on the effect of occupational stress on job performance in the nursing staff of a tertiary care teaching hospital in Surendranagar district. *Indian Journal of Community Health*, 33(1), 139–145. <https://doi.org/10.47203/IJCH.2021.v33i01.019>
- Kleka, P., Brycz, H., Zięba, M., & Fanslau, A. (2024). Longitudinal study of metacognition's role in self-efficacy and hope development. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 29379. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-80180-0>
- Kulmatycki, L., & Boroń-Krupińska, K. (2019). Relaxation state and self-efficacy in individuals participating in autogenic training. *Przegląd psychologiczny*, 62(3), 523–534. https://www.kul.pl/files/714/3.62.2019_art.5.eng.pdf
- Laela, S., Mustikasari, M., & Wardani, I. Y. (2018). Changes of symptoms and the ability of anxiety patients after exercise of thought stopping and family psychoeducation. *Media Keperawatan Indonesia*, 1(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.26714/mki.1.1.2018.1-11>
- Lamb, A. E., Biesecker, B. B., Umstead, K. L., Muratori, M., Biesecker, L. G., & Erby, L. H. (2016). Family functioning mediates adaptation in caregivers of individuals with Rett syndrome. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 99(11), 1873–1879. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2016.06.018>
- Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). *Stress, appraisal, and coping*. Springer publishing company.
- Lim, Y. C., Yobas, P., & Chen, H.-C. (2014). Efficacy of relaxation intervention on pain, self-efficacy, and stress-related variables in patients following total knee replacement surgery. *Pain Management Nursing*, 15(4), 888–896. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmn.2014.02.001>
- Lipshits-Braziler, Y., Tatar, M., & Gati, I. (2017). The effectiveness of strategies for coping with career indecision: Young adults' and career counselors' perceptions. *Journal of Career Development*, 44(5), 453–468. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894845316662705>
- Luberto, C. M., Hall, D. L., Park, E. R., Haramati, A., & Cotton, S. (2020). A perspective on the similarities and differences between mindfulness and relaxation. *Global advances in health and medicine*, 9, 2164956120905597. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2164956120905597>
- Melrose, S. (2019). Relocation stress in long term care: How staff can help. *Sherri Melrose Publications: A Virtual Memory Box*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppc.12341>
- Mughal, Z. (2023). Optimizing Workplace Training Transfer: A Case Study on Designing the 70: 20: 10 Training Strategy through SME and L&D Collaboration. <http://digital.library.wisc.edu/1793/84881>
- Nahlén Bose, C., Persson, H., Björling, G., Ljunggren, G., Elfström, M. L., & Saboonchi, F. (2016). Evaluation of a coping effectiveness training intervention in patients with chronic heart failure—a randomized controlled trial. *European Journal of Cardiovascular Nursing*, 15(7), 537–548. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1474515115625033>
- Paravlic, A. H., Tod, D., & Milanovic, Z. (2020). Mental simulation practice has beneficial effects on patients' physical function following lower limb arthroplasty: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, 101(8), 1447–1461. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2020.04.004>

- Paudel, D. (2020). ABC framework of fear of COVID-19 for psychotherapeutic intervention in Nepal: a review. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/9sj4a>
- Person, A. I., & Frazier, P. A. (2024). Coping strategy–situation fit vs. present control: relations with perceived stress in US college students. *Anxiety, Stress, & Coping*, 37(2), 219–232. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10615806.2023.2217099>
- Reeves, C. W., Nicholls, A. R., & McKenna, J. (2011). The effects of a coping intervention on coping self-efficacy, coping effectiveness, and subjective performance among adolescent soccer players. *International Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 9(2), 126–142. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1612197x.2011.567104>
- Riaz, S., Xu, Y., & Hussain, S. (2019). Workplace ostracism and knowledge hiding: the mediating role of job tension. *Sustainability*, 11(20), 5547. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11205547>
- Ruddell, P., Palmer, S., & Curwen, B. (2018). Brief cognitive behaviour therapy. *Brief Cognitive Behaviour Therapy*, 1–232. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781526447661>
- Seligman, M. E., Steen, T. A., Park, N., & Peterson, C. (2005). Positive psychology progress: empirical validation of interventions. *American psychologist*, 60(5), 410. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066x.60.5.410>
- Selva, J. (2021). Albert Ellis' ABC Model in the Cognitive Behavioral Therapy Spotlight. *PositivePsychology.com*.
- Shi, R., Sharpe, L., & Abbott, M. (2019). A meta-analysis of the relationship between anxiety and attentional control. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 72, 101754. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2019.101754>
- Tang, Y.-Y., Tang, R., Posner, M. I., & Gross, J. J. (2022). Effortless training of attention and self-control: mechanisms and applications. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 26(7), 567–577.
- Thomaes, S., Tjaarda, I. C., Brummelman, E., & Sedikides, C. (2020). Effort self-talk benefits the mathematics performance of children with negative competence beliefs. *Child Development*, 91(6), 2211–2220. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.13347>
- Van der Klink, J., Blonk, R., Schene, A. H., & Van Dijk, F. (2001). The benefits of interventions for work-related stress. *American Journal of Public Health*, 91(2), 270. <https://doi.org/10.2105/ajph.91.2.270>
- Waytz, A., Hershfield, H. E., & Tamir, D. I. (2015). Mental simulation and meaning in life. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 108(2), 336. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0038322>
- Wolfers, L. N., Lüpken, L. M., Schimmel, M., Utz, S., Nabi, R. L., & Gaiser, F. (2024). Coping with the COVID-19 pandemic by using media: extending the coping goodness-of-fit hypothesis to media use. *Communication Studies*, 75(5), 712–732. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10510974.2024.2365068>
- Wurst, S. A. (2016). Sportsmanship and Cognitive Psychology. *Sportsmanship: Multidisciplinary Perspectives*, 100. <https://doi.org/10.5860/choice.197890>
- Yawised, K., Apasrawirote, D., & Padgate, U. (2021). Enhancing SMEs' leader and business resilience towards digital marketing engagement during COVID-19 pandemic.
- Zhong, W., & Zhang, G. (2021). Mental simulation to promote exercise intentions and behaviors. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 589622. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.589622>